

Thermal shock and oxidation resistant gradient coating based on yttrium silicate for C/SiC composite

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SUMMARY

A novel yttrium silicate coating system is designed and fabricated by microwave sintering. BAS glass is adopted as the sintering additive to decrease the sintering temperature and make the coating denser, and celsian enhances the high temperature resistance. Green tape is firstly used to get homogenous coating with designed thickness on components.

Keywords: oxidation; coating; C/SiC composite; yttrium silicate; celsian glass-ceramic

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced silicon carbide (C/SiC) matrix composite is an attractive candidate for many applications in future spacecraft[1]. However, one of the formidable obstacles to the widespread use of C/SiC composite is that the carbon fibres oxidize at medium to high temperatures in an environment in which oxygen is present. Oxidation resistant coating is an effective approach[2-4].

Yttrium silicate coating[5, 6] is a promising candidate for oxidation resistant coating for its low oxygen diffusion coefficient and similar thermal expansion coefficient with silicon carbide. Webster et. al.[7] had prepared yttrium silicate coating on C/SiC using Y_2O_3/SiO_2 slips by slip casting and sintering. The selected sintering parameters were 3 h at 1600 °C in flowing argon. The coating can be effective at 1600 °C. The high sintering temperature may influence the mechanical property of C/SiC composite. Consequently, high sintering temperature and loose coating structure of yttrium silicate coating are great obstacles for high effectiveness.

Sintering additions are efficient choice to lower the sintering temperature and improving the densification process. In this work, BAS glass is selected as the additive and the effect of BAS glass content on the reaction of yttrium silicate was studied. Based on the result, a new gradient yttrium silicate coating is designed and the thermal shock and oxidation resistance is tested at 1400 °C.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The C/SiC composites used in this work were made with precursor infiltration and pyrolysis (PIP) method in the National University of Defense Technology in China. The samples were $10 \times 5 \times 4 \text{ mm}^3$ in size, with a density of 2.01 g/cm^3 . Before coating process, the samples were cleaned with distilled water and ethanol, and then dried at $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

BAS glass used in this work is prepared by fusion-quench method. The preparation details were reported in Ref.[8]. Yttrium oxide, silicon dioxide (Y:Si=1:1) and different weight percentages of BAS glass (2.5 %, 5 %, 10 %, 20 %) are mixed together. The mixed powders were compacted to bars with the size of $20 \times 5 \times 5 \text{ mm}^3$. The bar samples were sintered at $1350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h to get yttrium silicate.

Green-tape packing method was selected to prepare coatings. The mixtures are dispersed into proper organic solvent to get homogeneous slurry, which was made into green tape by tape casting. The thickness of each green tape is about $50 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The tape is cut out and covers the composite. From inner layer to outer layer, the percentage of BAS glass is 50%, 10%, 0%, respectively. The samples coated by green tapes were sintered at $1500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min by microwave. After microwave sintering process, a gradient yttrium silicate coating is fabricated.

The morphologies of the coatings are characterized by SEM, and the phase composition of the coating is characterized by XRD. The thermal shock and oxidation resistance is tested in air by cycled heating from $1400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to room temperature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of BAS Content on Sintering of Yttrium Silicate

Fig.1 shows the X-ray diffraction pattern of powder of fired bar samples with different BAS glass contents. BAS glass can significantly reduce the sintering temperature of yttrium silicate. When the content of BAS glass is greater than 5%, little Y_2O_3 and SiO_2 can be detected in the X-ray diffraction patterns. As shown in Fig.1, by adding BAS glass, Y_2O_3 can react with SiO_2 to form $\text{Y}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ and Y_2SiO_5 at only 1350°C . When the percentage of BAS glass is greater than 10%, $\text{Y}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ is the only resultant of reaction, whose thermal expansion coefficient is close to SiC. By increasing the contents of BAS glass, the diffraction peaks of celsian appeared in the X-ray diffraction patterns.

Fig.1 XRD patterns of B-50/B-10 and B-50/B-10/B-0 coatings

Morphologies of the Gradient Coating

According to the effect of BAS glass on the sintering of yttrium silicate, B-10 is chosen to be used as oxidation resistant coating, and B-50 is designed to fabricate the transition layer to bind the coating with composite tightly. To increase the 高温稳定性, B-0 coating is applied on the surface of the coating system. Double layered coating and three layered coating is fired at the same conditions. The fired coatings were dense and crack-free.

As Fig.2(a) and (c) illustrate, the three-layer coating and double layered coating are both dense, pore-free and crack-free after sintered at 1500°C. During sintering, the inner layer with high BAS glass content will soften firstly and the liquid BAS glass will seal the surface defects of composite and bind tightly with it. At the same time, BAS glass diffuse from inner layer to outer layer gradually and improve the densification of the coating. From the SEM photos the phase of crystals can be distinguished. In the double-layer coating, the crystals are small and disperse in the residual glass, while those are larger and strip in the three-layer coating.

Fig.2 Surface morphologies of B-50/B-10 (a)(b) and B-50/B-10/B-0 (c)(d) coatings

Fig.3 is the cross-section of fired B-50/B-10 and B-50/B-10/B-0 coating. Both coatings binds tightly with the composite. The average thickness of fired B-50/B-10 coating was 70 μm , and that of fired B-50/B-10/B-0 coating was around 100 μm . The shrinkage of green tape is 30-35%.

As Fig.3 (a) and (b) show, there are big white crystals disperse into the grey BAS glass matrix of B-50/B-10 coating. Some little celsian particles, which is characterized as stick shape, lie in the BAS glass. Because of the high molting point of celsian, the celsian particles can hence the softening temperature of the coating. On the other hand, the stick crystals dispersed in the glass will improve the mechanical properties. As Fig.3 (c) and (d) show, the B-50/B-10/B-0 coating is a little loser than the B-50/B-10 coating, but the residual grey BAS glass is less. Both coatings have no obviously interlayer,

Fig. 3 Cross-section morphologies of B-50/B-10 (a)(b) and B-50/B-10/B-0 (c)(d) coating

Phase compositions of fired yttrium silicate coating

Fig. 4 shows the X-ray diffraction patterns of the fired coatings. The main phase composition of both coatings is $Y_2Si_2O_7$. Meanwhile, some weak diffraction peaks according with hexacelsian appeared in both patterns. The intensity of some diffraction peaks increase greatly in both patterns, which may be caused by preferred growth directions of crystals. Consequently, the content of $Y_2Si_2O_7$ can not be characterized by the intensity of diffraction peaks.

Fig.4 Phase composition of sintered Y_2O_3 and SiO_2 with different BAS glass content

Oxidation Tests

The thermal shock and oxidation resistance of both coated samples were tested at 1400° C. The coatings remain dense and crack-free after 11 times of thermal shocks from 1400 °C to room temperature. After tests, the B-50/B-10/B-0 coating was dense and change little, while the B-50/B-10 coating turned glassy and transparent.

In the first four thermal shock tests, the weight losses of two coated samples were similar. In the following tests, the weight loss of three layer coated sample increased more slowly than double layer coated sample. After thermal shocks of 11 times and oxidation for 110 min, the weight loss of the B-50/B-10/B-0 coated sample was only 0.8726%.

Fig. 5 Weight loss curves of B-50/B-10 and B-50/B-10/B-0 coated samples oxidized at 1400°C

The inner layer of the coating with high BAS content, The thermal expansion coefficient of $Y_2Si_2O_7$ is $2 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}C$, which is close to C/SiC composite. $Y_2Si_2O_7$ in B-50/B-10/B-0 coating is more than that in B-50/B-10 coating. As a result, the thermal expansion coefficient of B-50/B-10/B-0 coating is lower and closer to the composite than B-50/B-10 coating. The residual BAS glass makes the coating bind tightly with the composite. The B-50/B-10/B-0 coating can resist thermal shocks well and protect the composite from oxidation.

Conclusions

- (1) BAS glass is an effective addition to singter yttrium silicate, which can lower the reaction temperature of Y_2O_3 and SiO_2 to 1350 °C.
- (2) B-50/B-10/B-0 gradient yttrium silicate coating was designed and fabricated. The dense coating have low expansion coefficient, good bind with the composite and self-sealing ability. Consequently, it has excellent thermal shock and oxidation resistance.

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